

Achieving Multiple-Day Stability in a Single-Cavity Dual-Comb laser for Spectroscopic Applications.

Alberto Rodriguez Cuevas
¹Aston Institute of Photonic
Technologies, College of Engineering
and Physical Sciences, Aston
University B4 7ET Birmingham,
United Kingdom
<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4772-9427>

Dmitrii Storialov
¹Aston Institute of Photonic
Technologies, College of Engineering
and Physical Sciences, Aston
University B4 7ET Birmingham,
United Kingdom
<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8635-2346>

Hani Khashi
¹Aston Institute of Photonic
Technologies, College of Engineering
and Physical Sciences, Aston
University B4 7ET Birmingham,
United Kingdom
<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6343-248X>

Sergey Sergeyev
¹Aston Institute of Photonic
Technologies, College of Engineering
and Physical Sciences, Aston
University B4 7ET Birmingham,
United Kingdom
<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1515-5019>

Abstract: A portable ring cavity fiber laser that generates two stable orthogonally polarized vector solitons for over 125 hours. Featuring an Allan deviation of 0.0002319 Hz/s and a single sideband (SSB) phase noise of -95 dBc/Hz at an offset of 100 Hz.

1. Dual-comb systems in a single cavity.

Dual-comb systems find applications across spectroscopy, Light Detection and Ranging (LIDAR), and optical communications [1]. However, their widespread adoption has been hindered by the need for intricate and costly phase-locking mechanisms, rendering many systems impractical for industrial use and limiting their deployment primarily to research purposes. Efforts have intensified to create simpler and more affordable systems in response to this challenge. A promising approach involves the simultaneous generation of two orthogonally polarized vector solitons within a single laser cavity [2]. Presently, various methods—such as wavelength-multiplexing, cavity-space multiplexing, polarization multiplexing, bidirectional circulation, and extra-cavity generation—have been explored, each with its own versions and sub-variants [2]. This work focuses on polarization multiplexing due to its selection based on the results obtained from prior studies [3,4], leveraging previously acquired knowledge. Additionally, it shows potential for out-of-lab ellipsometry ranging applications. The primary advantage of this approach lies in its relative simplicity compared to other methods, while its chief challenge remains ensuring long-term stability—a concern evident in the scarcity of published results demonstrating prolonged stability.

2. Portable Ring Cavity Laser.

The optimized laser cavity described in this paper is schematically represented in the figure 1. It is a 5.26 meters long cavity that is pumped by a 980 nm laser diode. It has a Wavelength Division Multiplexing (WDM) as the cavity input to combine the continuous wave light of the laser at 980 nm with the pulses already circulating within the cavity. Inside the cavity there is a segment of 0.17 m of Er³⁺-doped fiber (ER110-4/125) exhibiting a group velocity dispersion (GVD) parameter of -15 ps/km/nm. A 0.5-meter PM-1550 fiber, possessing a GVD of 18.2 ps/km/nm, facilitates the generation of a polarization multiplexing mode-locked regime. Achieving this polarization multiplexing required adjustments to the polarization states within the cavity. Therefore, there is a 3-paddle polarization controller, and each paddle has a diameter of 28 mm. This polarization controller is positioned after the PM fiber. To ensure unidirectional propagation, a 51 dB dual-stage polarization-independent optical isolator (Thorlabs IOT-H-1550A) has been introduced into the laser cavity. Additionally, a film-type homemade single-wall carbon nanotube (CNT) absorber that has been inserted between two FC/UPC connectors serves as the main mode locking component. The cavity concludes with an output fiber coupler redirecting 25% of the light outside the cavity. When comparing the structure of this cavity with the cavity used in the previous works [3, 4] we can highlight four main changes. The cavity is shorter 5.26m as compared to 17.3 m in the previous occasion and so the fundamental repetition rate is now 39.25 MHz (25.47ns round-trip time) instead of 11.95 MHz (83 ns round-trip time). To reduce the cavity length a shorter segment of Er doped fiber is used but with a higher concentration to compensate for the effect. The higher output percentage in the coupler in combination with the shorter cavity length generates a slightly smaller output power in the cavity, 0.2 mW, in comparison to 0.5 mW nonetheless, the circulating power inside the cavity is much smaller, according to our estimations 6.25 times smaller (0.8 mW compared to 5 mW). This lower intra cavity optical power helps with the stability since the CNT is quite fragile to high powers.

3. Results.

Figure 1 illustrates the laser cavity used in this work and its spectral and frequency stability. Both combs coexist for over 125 hours, although with notable fluctuations influenced by external temperature variations [4]. Initially, over

53.5 hours, the difference between the combs progressively increases at a rate of 0.6257 Hz per hour (Allan deviation of 0.0001738 Hz/s), elevating from 1108.725 Hz to 1142.2 Hz. Subsequently, a decreasing stage spanning 20 hours sees the frequency difference decrease to less than 1125.5 Hz (Allan deviation of 0.0002319 Hz/s). Notably, the highest Allan deviation, lasting 4 hours, reached 0.00056 Hz/s.

Modifications made to the laser setup compared to previous demonstrations [3,4] have substantially improved stability by a factor of 17, extending it from 7 hours to 125 hours. Additionally, the single sideband (SSB) phase noise has significantly reduced, plummeting from -70 dBc/Hz to -95 dBc/Hz at a 100 Hz offset frequency. These improvements are attributed to several modifications: reduction in total cavity length, decrease in gain media length while increasing doping levels, secure winding of optical fibers within 3D printed spools to prevent movement, and external isolation of all components within a custom housing, mitigating external perturbations. Moreover, the refined regime within the cavity not only becomes more accessible but also offers superior control. The laser, tested when connected to a fiber collimator, was utilized in a dual-comb ranging device [5], showcasing its capability to capture spectroscopic signatures and distances from detected targets.

Figure 1: Dual-comb system and stability. a) Dual-comb laser cavity for LIDAR configuration. b) Frequency difference stability and Allan deviation obtained from the measures of the Figure 1 c). c) Spectral stability obtained from OSA measurements. d) RF stability obtained from RF measurements.

4. References

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